

Unlocking flexibility potential and grid balancing of buildings using sorption thermal energy storage: Examining different charging and discharging scenarios

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ABSTRACT

The demand for clean and renewable alternatives is rising due to the increased global warming concerns. Solar and wind energy resources offer promising solutions for power generation. Due to the natural intermittent of these resources, the use of energy storage systems, specifically in buildings, promotes grid balancing and building flexibility. The present study develops and simulates a novel sorption energy storage system for weekly storage solutions based on different charging and discharging scenarios. Various charging power of 2:10 kW with a limiting temperature of 90 °C—capitalizes on surplus solar and wind energies or off-peak electricity—is used to charge an adsorbent material (CaCl₂-silica gel) up to attaining 100%SOC, at condensation temperatures of 15 and 20 °C. Subsequently, the sorption energy system discharges heating at evaporation temperatures of 10 and 15 °C. The results showed that the charging time decreased from 10.8 to 3.8 h with increasing the power from 2 to 10 kW, at a condensation temperature of 15 °C, achieving a volumetric and gravimetric energy density (ESD) of 134 kWh/m³ and 650 kJ/kg, respectively. Overall, the use of sorption energy storage systems opens new avenues for promoting and unlocking flexibility potential and grid balancing of buildings.

KEYWORDS

Building flexibility, Charging, Discharging, Grid balance, Sorption thermal energy storage.

INTRODUCTION

Buildings account for 33% of global energy demand especially EU domestic hot water and space heating make up 14.8 and 63.6%, respectively. To increase energy efficiency and exploit surplus power from renewable/grid sources, sorption thermal energy storage (STES) systems are essential to supply the thermal energy demand of buildings. The use of STES systems is advantageous due to their superior energy storage densities over sensible and latent heat storage systems, and negligible heat storage losses during idle processes—it only loses sensible heating. This makes those systems favorable for weekly and seasonal heat storage. Besides, STES systems can store and release according to the buildings' demands, and ambient boundary conditions [1]. Several studies have been carried out to investigate the thermal performance of STES for domestic heating. For instance, Crespo et al. [1] used a solar-driven seasonal sorption storage system for residential applications, attaining volumetric energy storage density of 90 and 106 kWh/m³, with 35% of the heat demand for a single family house. Ma et al. [2] showed the feasibility of solar TES using NH₃ chemisorption for heating applications, covering 18.6% of heating demand due to limited discharge temperature.

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However, several studies have examined the use of STES for building applications, the use of integrated storage/building systems for heating applications is unsatisfactory and entails a deep analysis of charging/discharging performance and the feasibility of power-to-heat processes.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND WORKING PRINCIPLES

Fig. 1 shows the charging and discharging modes of a novel STES. During charging mode, the sorption reactors are charging with surplus power from buildings, while the condensation heat is rejected in a heat exchanger (condenser) using a dry cooler. For discharging mode, the evaporation heat is delivered via a dry heater or heat pump, and the discharged heat from the sorption reactors is used for heating buildings. The working principles of STES systems include reversible reactions between sorbate (water vapor) and sorbent material (CaCl₂-silica gel). During the charging mode (desorption), the sorbent desorbs the sorbate via an endothermic reaction. In idle mode, the adsorption of heat is stored in the sorbent and the total heat storage is only losses trivial sensible heat losses. During the discharging mode (adsorption), the adsorbate is stated to be adsorbed by the sorbent, undergoing an exothermic process. This heat can be used for heating processes to supply it to end users in buildings [3].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a sorption thermal energy storage (STES) system.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Adsorption kinetics and isotherms

A complete analysis of STEES is modeled based on [4]. The sorption rate of the composite CaCl₂-SG/water pair is governed by the linear driving force (LDF) model as follows:

$$\frac{dw}{dt} = k(W - w) \quad (1)$$

The Dubinin–Astakhov (DA) equation is derived as follows:

$$W = W_{max} \exp(-kA^n) \quad (2)$$

$$A = RT \ln\left(\frac{p_{sat}}{p}\right) \quad (3)$$

here, p_{sat} [mbar] is the saturated water vapor pressure at the sorption temperature T [K], and p [mbar] is the sorption pressure.

Energy balance

The energy balance of the sorber reactor is simulated using lumped parameter modeling:

$$(Mc_p)_{sorb} \frac{dT_{sorb}}{dt} = M_{sg} Q_{st} \frac{dq}{dt} + \dot{m} c_{p,HT/MT} (T_{in} - T_{out}) - UA_{loss}(T_{sorb} - T_{amb}) \quad (4)$$

The energy balance for both the condenser and evaporator is given as:

$$(Mc_p)_{cond/evap} \frac{dT_{cond/cond}}{dt} = -[M_{sg} L] \frac{dq}{dt} + \dot{m} c_{p,MT/LT} (T_{in} - T_{out}) \quad (5)$$

The outlet temperature of the sorber and the condenser/evaporator is estimated as follows:

$$T_{HX,out} = T_{HX} + (T_{HX,in} - T_{HX}) \exp\left(\frac{-UA_{HX}}{\dot{m}_w c_{p,w}}\right) \quad (6)$$

The main specifications of STES are listed in Table 1.

Water tank

After estimating the increase/decrease in the mass flow rate of circulating water, the water tank height can be evaluated as:

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = \left[-M_{sg} \frac{dw}{dt}\right] / (\rho_w A_{base}) \quad (7)$$

here A_{base} is the base area of the water tank.

Table 1 Main factors of the adsorption cooling system.

Factor	Value	Unit
M_s	100	kg
$(Mc_p)_{sorb}$	169.8	kJ/kg
$(Mc_p)_{cond/evap}$	20.9	kJ/kg
$UA_{ads/des}$	4.0	kW/K
$UA_{cond/evap}$	2.0	kW/K
\dot{m}_{HT}	1.0	m ³ /h
\dot{m}_{MT}	1.5	m ³ /h
\dot{m}_{LT}	0.5	m ³ /h

Performance metrics

The thermal energy storage power and SOC can be evaluated as follows:

$$Q_{charg/disch} = \dot{m} c_{p,HT/MT} (T_{in} - T_{out}) \quad (8)$$

$$SOC = \frac{H}{H_{max}} \times 100\%, SOD = 1 - \frac{H}{H_{max}} \quad (9)$$

METHODS

A numerical simulation of STES is developed and simulated using Simulink. Herein, the mass and energy balance of STES are simulated for charging and discharging modes based on different charging powers, condensation, and evaporation temperatures, for evaluating their performance in terms of energy storage, and volumetric/gravimetric ESD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The charging characteristics of STES are investigated using different charging powers of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 kW, at two condensation temperatures of 15 and 20 °C, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the increase in charging powers results in reducing the charging time. The results show that increasing the charging power from 2 to 10 kW, reduces the charging time from 10.8 to 3.6 h, and from 11 to 4.5 h, for condensation temperatures of 15 and 20 °C, respectively. Besides, the thermal propagation of sorption material is faster under higher charging powers. The sorption uptake decreases faster at higher charging powers. Consequently, the tank height and SOC are faster for upgraded powers. Fig. 3 shows the complete charging time, total charged energy (E), volumetric ESD (ESD_v), and gravimetric ESD (ESD_m). It can be seen that the increase

in the condensation temperature leads to elongated charging time and limited performance indicators (i.e., E, ESD_v, and ESD_m). It can be seen that the performance indicators slightly increase with the increase in the charging power. While increasing the condensation temperature reduces E, ESD_v, and ESD_m. At condensation temperature of 15 °C, E, ESD_v, and ESD_m are 18 kWh, 133-134 kWh/m³, and 647-650 kJ/kg, while at condensation temperature of 20 °C their values are 17.6 kWh, 130 kWh/m³, and 633-635 kJ/kg. This reduction is mainly due to the drop in Δw for higher T_{Cond}.

Figure 2. Effect of charging power and condensation temperature on charging characteristics.

Figure 3. Charging performance under different charging power and condensation temperatures.

The discharging characteristics of STES are investigated at two evaporation temperatures of 10 and 15 °C while keeping the adsorption temperature to 30 °C, as shown in Fig. 4. The increase in the evaporation temperature from 10 to 15 °C, increases the discharge time from 2.6 to 3.4 h. The discharging time is limited to a discharging temperature of 32 °C. This means that the discharging temperature varies from 90 to 30 °C to cover the heating load of a building. As a result, the sorption kinetics is faster and leads to an elevated Δw . Therefore, the reduction in the tank height is more significant and steeper for SOD under higher evaporation temperatures. Due to the limited discharging temperature of 32 °C, the SOD reaches 21% and 19.4% at evaporation temperatures of 10 and 15 °C, respectively.

Fig. 5 reveals the complete discharging time, total E, ESD_v , and ESD_m . The results exhibit that the increase in the evaporation temperature leads to elongated charging time and the performance indicators (i.e., E, ESD_v , and ESD_m) are increasing appreciably. The increase in the evaporation temperature from 10 to 15 °C increases E, ESD_v , and ESD_m . At evaporation temperature of 10 °C, E, ESD_v , and ESD_m are 18.9 kWh, 139.5 kWh/m³, and 678.6 kJ/kg, while condensation temperature of 20 °C their values are 24.7 kWh, 182.8 kWh/m³, and 889.1 kJ/kg. This reduction is mainly due to the drop in Δw for higher T_{Cond} . This increment in the discharging performance is attributed to the reduction in the difference between adsorption temperature (MT) and evaporation temperature (LT). Interestingly, it can be noted that the charging and discharging performance are highly dependent on the boundary conditions.

Figure 4. Effect of evaporation temperatures on discharging characteristics.

Figure 5. Discharging performance under different evaporation temperatures.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a numerical simulation for STES systems is developed to examine the flexibility potential and grid balancing of buildings. The charging and discharging storage are developed to highlight the system performance in terms of charging/discharging time, energy storage, and volumetric/gravimetric ESD. The following conclusion can be drawn:

- The increase in the charging power from 10 to 2 kW reduces the charging time from 10.8 to 3.8 h, and 11 to 4.5 h, at a condensation temperature of 15 and 20 °C, respectively.
- Increasing the condensation temperature from 15 to 20 °C reduces charging ESD_v from ~134 to 130 kWh/m³ and ESD_m from ~650 to 635 kJ/kg.
- Increasing the evaporation temperature (10 to 15 °C) increases discharging time by 28%.
- Increasing the condensation temperature from 15 to 20 °C, increasing discharging ESD_v from 139.5 to 182.8 kWh/m³, and ESD_m from 678.6 to 889.1 kJ/kg.

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